

Moderation Role of Interest in the Relationship between Product Quality and Price on Loyalty with Satisfaction as a Mediation on Iphone Users in Banda Aceh

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Abstract: This research aims to examine the moderating role of interest in product quality and price influence on loyalty and its satisfaction as a mediator on iPhone users in Banda Aceh city, Indonesia. The population was iPhone users in Banda Aceh City. The sample was determined based on Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) requirement, using the formula 5 times the indicators, so it was 5x 27 indicators totaling 135 respondents. Data were tested by SEM method with AMOS software. The result shows Product quality affected satisfaction, Price affected satisfaction, Product Quality affected Loyalty, Price did not affect Loyalty, Interest affected loyalty, Satisfaction affected loyalty, Satisfaction partially mediated the product quality role in loyalty, Satisfaction fully mediated the price role in loyalty, Interest (quasi) Moderated the Product Quality role in Loyalty, and Interest (quasi) Moderated the Price role in Loyalty. These findings prove that the loyalty-strengthening model for iPhone users in Banda Aceh city is a function of increasing product quality and price compatibility, which is strengthened by increased interest, and also with the contribution of increased satisfaction.

Keywords: Loyalty, Satisfaction, Interest, Product Quality, Price

I. Introduction

Global technological developments make all technological goods undergo rapid changes to suit individual lifestyles. One that is developing rapidly is mobile phones, which nowadays are more often referred to as smartphones. In 2016 smartphone users in Indonesia reached 132.7 million people, of which Indonesia's population was 256.2 million people. The demand for smartphones in Indonesia and globally which continues to increase makes manufacturers continue to compete to innovate on smartphone products. This makes the competition in the smartphone market very tight. In 2017 internet market research company. Indonesia reports that 90% of internet usage by Indonesian netizens are internet users using smartphones (tribunnews.com). Based on eMarketer research, explains that the percentage of smartphone users and penetration in the world from 2014 to 2020 is expected to continue to increase. This statistical data shows the number of smartphone or smartphone users worldwide from 2014 to 2020. In 2014, the number of smartphone users reached 1.57 billion. And it is estimated that in 2020 smartphone users will reach 2.87 billion users. Looking at the development of smartphone users, which continues to increase from year to year, Indonesia turns out to be one of the countries that have the most smartphone users, ranking 6th out of 50 countries.

Starting to research sourced from eMarketer, in 2016 smartphone users were as much as 65.2 million users, in 2017 it increased to 74.9 million users, in 2018 it increased again to 83.5 million users, and the estimated increase obtained from the databox sourced from eMarketer, in 2019 users smartphones will increase again to 92 million users. Smartphones, currently there are many choices of types of smartphones on the market. Apple is one of the brands whose sales are increasing day by day. Apple shocked the world on June 29, 2007, when they decided to openly enter the arena of mobile phone competition. Apple exclusively hooked AT & T wireless as a partner for the first generation iPhone, which was named the iPhone 2G. When it was first developed, Apple wanted to make the iPhone a mobile phone unit that combines the entertainment features of the iPod with the telecommunications function of a mobile phone. Moreover, the iPhone 2G is equipped with a 2-megapixel camera for photography needs. At the end of 2007, the iPhone successfully sold more than 3 million units of the iPhone 2G and even penetrated the 6 million unit mark. iPhone itself is a smartphone made by Apple that uses the iOS operating system on its device, iOS is a mobile operating system

developed and distributed by the company Apple Inc. The iOS operating system was first launched in 2007 for use on iPhone and iPod Touch products, but now iOS has been developed to support other Apple devices such as the iPad and Apple TV. Unlike other operating systems such as Windows Phone (Windows CE) from Microsoft and Android from Google, Apple does not license iOS to be installed on non-Apple-made hardware.

Apple products themselves are certainly not foreign to the world community, including Indonesia. The variety of product lines that Apple has, of course, makes it easier for consumers to choose which types of products to buy according to their needs. This also provides benefits for sales of Apple products because the linkage of products with one another will make consumers not only buy one product but also buy other Apple products to support the performance of the smartphones they already have. Apple's smartphone comes by positioning its products in the upper middle market segment. This brand of smartphone is in great demand by consumers because it suits their needs as well as with good quality so that Apple smartphones can be accepted by the smartphone market.

Table 1. Smartphone Market Share in Indonesia

Brand	2018	2019	2020
Samsung	12%	18%	20%
Apple	53%	37%	20%
Huawei	9%	13%	15%
Xiaomi	7%	9%	12%
Oppo	5%	7%	9%

Source: sound.com. 2020

Based on the data presented in Table 1 regarding smartphone sales data in Indonesia in 2018-2020 above, the phenomenon that occurs shows that Apple sales experienced a decline in market share sales in 2018 from 53% to 37% in 2019 and again decreased in 2018. in 2020 to 20% this is an interesting phenomenon to study because there is a gap where smartphone sales increase industrially but iPhones experience a decline in sales or market share. The decline in the iPhone can be caused by the lack of satisfaction of consumers with iPhone products so they do not have loyalty to iPhone products. Loyalty is the customer's intention to buy a product that has been purchased in the past. Loyalty is the behavior of consumers who want to buy or not buy a product (Kotler & Keller, 2018). According to (Kotler & Keller, 2018) in the buying process, willingness to repurchase or willingness to repurchase is closely related to motivation to use or buy certain products. For each customer, the motivation for this purchase is different.

Many factors affect customer loyalty, one of which is customer satisfaction. (Tjiptono, 2017) defines customer satisfaction as an emotional response to experiences related to certain purchased products. The initial survey of this research in Banda Aceh city, Indonesia, reveals customers are not very satisfied because the average value obtained is 3.02. This indicates that customer satisfaction with iPhone products in Banda Aceh City is not too good. The next factor is product quality. Customer loyalty is one of the important factors for the continued development of the company and for increasing company sales. Businesses in the food sector will benefit greatly when they can create satisfaction in every customer, satisfied customers will form their loyalty to the company. The results of research by (Anggraeni, Kumadji, & Sunarti, 2016) show that product quality affects loyalty. The initial survey of this research reveals customers are not very satisfied with the quality of the product because the average value obtained is 3.40, this shows that the quality of iPhone products in Banda Aceh City is not very good.

The next factor is also price. Price is also a consideration for customer loyalty in choosing a product. In general, consumers tend to choose companies that offer their products at relatively low and consistent prices. However, people still think that aluminum products from PT Alakasa Extrusindo are quite expensive because the composition of the processing of raw materials is not mixed with other materials, it can be said according to consumer demand. The results of (Kumala & Anwar, 2020) show that price affects loyalty. The initial survey of this research reveals customers are not very satisfied with the price of the product because the average value obtained is 3.20, this shows that the price of the iPhone in Banda Aceh City is not too good.

The next factor is interest. In addition to service, customer interest is also something that must be needed, psychological aspects and not only color a person's behavior to carry out activities that cause someone to feel attracted to something. Factors that influence the emergence of a person's interest to depend on physical, social, emotional, and experience needs. Interest begins with feelings of pleasure and a positive attitude. This interest is not static or also stopped, but dynamic and also has its ups and downs. Interest is also not innate, but something that can be learned. That is, something that was previously uninterested can turn into something that is of interest because of certain inputs or new insights and new patterns of thinking. The initial survey of this research reveals customers are not very satisfied

with the interest because the average value obtained is 3.24, this shows that the interest in iPhone products in Banda Aceh City is not very good.

II. Literature

Loyalty

(Sangadji & Sopiah, 2014) say loyalty refers to the behavior of decision-making units to make continuous purchases of goods or services from a selected company. With purchases made by customers continuously can provide long-term benefits for the company. Meanwhile, (Tjiptono, 2017) suggests that customer loyalty is a customer's commitment to a brand, store, or supplier, based on a very positive attitude and is reflected in consistent repeat purchases. (Nurullaili & Wijayanto, 2013) explains the factors that influence loyalty are price, service, product quality, and promotion factors. (Hidayat, 2009) states customer loyalty is a customer's commitment to a market based on a positive attitude and is reflected in consistent repeat purchases. He also said the indicators of customer loyalty are Trust, Emotion commitment, Switching cost, Word of mouth, and Cooperation.

Satisfaction

According to (Zeithaml, Bitner, & Gremler, 2018) customer satisfaction is a fulfillment response from customers to a product or service itself that has met customer needs and expectations. Furthermore, according to (Kotler & Keller, 2018) Customer satisfaction is the level of one's feelings after comparing the perceived (performance or results) compared to their expectations. Meanwhile, according to (Parasuraman, Zeithaml, & Malhotra, 2005), customer satisfaction is the customer's feeling about the type of service he gets (Firmansyah, 2017). According to (Firmansyah, 2017) the factors that affect the satisfaction of customers are: Quality of service or services, Product quality, Price, Situational factors, and Personal factors from customers. (Kotler & Keller, 2018) say satisfaction indicators are: Satisfaction, Repeat purchase, Word of Mouth/Buzz, Evangelism, and Ownership.

Interest

Purchase intention represents what we think about buying (Toufani, Stanton, & Chikweche, 2017). Sometimes buying interest is often associated with the consumer's desire to buy a product. The emergence of this desire also shows a person's willingness to buy a product that is selected based on references, experience, and external factors (Lau, Lam, & Cheung, 2016). The same thing was said by Safin et al. (2016) that although buying interest only crosses the minds of consumers, it can already be said that buying interest is. While in the research conducted by (Rahim, Safin, Kheng, Abas, & Ali, 2016) buying interest is defined as planning a purchase in the future, but not necessarily purchasing because it depends on the ability of the individual. The indicators of buying interest according to (Pramono & Ferdinand, 2012) are: Transactional interest, Referential interest, Preferential interest, and Explorative interest.

Product Quality

(Kotler & Keller, 2018) state product quality is the totality of features and characteristics of a product or service that depend on the ability to satisfy the needs that are asked or implied. (Yamit, 2013) defines quality as anything that consumers need and want. (Wijaya, 2018) defines the quality of goods and services as the overall combination of characteristics of goods and services according to marketing, engineering, production, and maintenance that makes the goods and services used to meet the expectations of customers or consumers. According to (Kotler & Keller, 2012), there are nine dimensions of product quality, namely: Form, Product features, Performance, Accuracy/conformance, Durability, Reliability, Ease of repair, Style, and Design.

Price

According to (Tjiptono, 2017) prices are directly related to income and profit. Price is the only element of the marketing mix that generates revenue for the company. (Tjiptono, 2017) price is the value of a product "a statement of value". Value is the ratio or comparison between perceived benefits and the costs incurred to obtain the product (such as reliability, durability, performance, and resale value). According to the opinion of the experts above, it can be concluded that the price is the amount of money needed to exchange it for products or services that can meet customer needs as well as one of the marketing mix elements that plays an important role in marketing. (Kotler & Keller, 2012) define four indicators that characterize prices, namely: Price affordability, Price compatibility with product value, Price competitiveness, and Price compatibility with benefits.

Hypothesis

Based on the causality literature and the case to be examined, the hypothesis of this study was determined as follows.

H1 : Product quality affected satisfaction,

- H2 : Price affected satisfaction,
- H3 : Product Quality affected Loyalty,
- H4 : Price affected Loyalty,
- H5 : Interest affected loyalty,
- H6 : Satisfaction affected loyalty,
- H7 : Satisfaction mediated the product quality role in loyalty,
- H8 : Satisfaction mediated the price role in loyalty,
- H9 : Interest Moderated the Product Quality role in Loyalty
- H10 : Interest Moderated the Price role in Loyalty.

III. Method

The population in this research was iPhone users in Banda Aceh City. Purposive sampling was used to select the respondents. The sample was determined based on the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) requirement using the formula 5 times the indicators, so it was 5 x 27 indicators (Ferdinand, 2014), totaling 135 samples. This study used the SEM method to test the data, by using AMOS software. The mediation variable was Satisfaction, while the exogenous was Product Quality and Price, the endogenous was Loyalty, and the moderating was Interest.

IV. Result

After the confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) has been carried out and meets all the criteria (goodness of fit and loading factor), the Structural test was processed as the next testing step, as shown below.

Figure 2.SEM Test

The testing was done by providing the Critical Ratio (CR) and the significance (p) as shown in Table 2 below.

Table 2
Standardized Regression

			Estimate	SE	CR	P
Satisfaction	<---	Price	0.668	0.108	5,636	0.000
Satisfaction	<---	Product Quality	0.372	0.104	2,790	0.033
Loyalty	<---	Interest	0.817	0.106	3,606	0.000
Loyalty	<---	Price	0.290	0.101	2,105	0.038
Loyalty	<---	Product Quality	0.229	0.106	2,300	0.041
Loyalty	<---	Satisfaction	0.321	0.067	2,624	0.036

Source: Primary Data Processed, (2022)

Product Quality role in Satisfaction (H1)

Product quality role test in Satisfaction obtained a significance of 0.033. This concludes product quality affected satisfaction. The Product Quality role size in Satisfaction is 0.372 or 37.2%. This explains that the better the product quality the higher satisfaction. In using a product or service, consumers will compare the costs or efforts incurred with the benefits or benefits that have been obtained by consumers to create customer value. (Rangkuti, 2013) states product value as a comprehensive assessment of the benefits of a product, based on customer perceptions of what has been received by the customer and what has been given by the product, while Woodruff in (Kristanto, 2018) suggests that the product value has a close relationship with consumer satisfaction.

Price role in Satisfaction (H2)

The price role test in Satisfaction obtained a significance of 0.000. This explains the price affected increasing satisfaction. The price role size in satisfaction is 0.668 or 66.8%. This explains the higher the price, the higher the satisfaction. (Purnamasari, Suwena, & Haris, 2015) explains that the price for customers is an important consideration for customers to buy products at a company because the price of a product affected customer perceptions of the product. Still, (Purnamasari et al., 2015), reveals price is one of the things that can affect customer satisfaction. Therefore, the issue of price also needs to be reviewed concerning customer satisfaction. (Lonardo & Soelasih, 2014) show price affected customer satisfaction.

Product Quality role in Loyalty (H3)

Product quality role test in Loyalty obtained $p = 0.041$. This describes product quality affected loyalty. The Product Quality role size in loyalty is 0.229 or 22.9%. This explains the higher the product quality the higher the loyalty. Loyalty is customer loyalty to make repeated purchases of the products offered by the company. Customer loyalty is one of the important factors for the continued development of the company and for increasing company sales. Businesses in the food sector will benefit greatly when they can create satisfaction in every customer, satisfied customers will form their loyalty to the company. The results of research by (Anggraeni et al., 2016) show that product quality affected loyalty.

Price role in Loyalty (H4)

Price role test in loyalty obtained $p = 0.048$. This explains price affected loyalty because the p obtained is < 0.05 . Price is also a consideration for customer loyalty in choosing a product. In general, consumers tend to choose companies that offer their products at relatively low and consistent prices. However, people still think that aluminum products from PT Alakasa Extrusindo are quite expensive because the composition of the processing of raw materials is not mixed with other materials, it can be said according to consumer demand. The results of (Kumala & Anwar, 2020) show that price affected loyalty.

Interest role in Loyalty (H5)

Interest role test in Loyalty obtained $p = 0.000$. This describes interest affected loyalty. The Product Quality role size in loyalty is 0.817 or 81.7%. This describes the higher the interest the higher the loyalty. Buying interest is a consumer response that appears to an object that shows a person's desire to make a purchase. Consumers who have an interest in buying something show their attention and pleasure towards a product which is followed by the realization of buying behavior. According to (Hasan, 2010) that customer loyalty is a customer who only does not repurchase an item or service, for example by recommending others to buy. The more competition in the culinary world, the consumers will be more selective in choosing a place to eat (Segoro, 2017). (Nurkhalik, 2020) found interest affected loyalty.

Satisfaction role in Loyalty (H6)

Satisfaction role test in Loyalty obtained $p = 0.036$. This figures Satisfaction affected Loyalty. The Satisfaction role size in Loyalty is 0.321 or 32.1%. This reveals the higher the satisfaction the higher the loyalty. (Tjiptono, 2017) defines customer satisfaction as an emotional response to experiences related to certain purchased products or services, retail outlets, or even behavioral patterns (such as shopping behavior and buyer behavior), as well as the market as a whole. While loyalty is a customer's commitment to a brand, store, or supplier, based on a very positive attitude and is reflected in consistent repeat purchases.

Product Quality contribution to Loyalty thru Satisfaction (H7)

Thru the Sobel calculation, the H7 test provides the result as 2.866 and is significant at = 0.004. Thus, Satisfaction acted as a mediator between Product Quality and Loyalty. Thus, because satisfaction affected and acted as a mediator, product quality affected loyalty, then the satisfaction role between product quality and loyalty is partial. Partial mediation means that the Product Quality affected Loyalty both within of without Satisfaction as a mediator.

Table 3

**Sobel Product Quality Test Results
To Loyalty Through Satisfaction**

Input:		Test statistic:	Std. Error:	p-value:
a	0.372	Sobel test: 2.86622967	0.0416617	0.00415393
b	0.321	Aroian test: 2.82696277	0.04224039	0.00469918
s _a	0.104	Goodman test: 2.90717965	0.04107486	0.00364704
s _b	0.067	Reset all	Calculate	

Price contribution to Loyalty thru Satisfaction (H8)

Thru the Sobel calculation, the H8 test provides the result of 3.787 and its significance is 0.000. Thus, Satisfaction acted as a mediator between Price and Loyalty. Thus, because satisfaction affected and acted as a mediator, price did not affect loyalty, then the satisfaction role between price and loyalty is Full. Full mediation means that the Price only can affect Loyalty indirectly thru Satisfaction.

**Table 4
Sobel Test Price Results
To Loyalty Through Satisfaction**

Input:		Test statistic:	Std. Error:	p-value:
a	0.668	Sobel test: 3.78764726	0.05661245	0.00015208
b	0.321	Aroian test: 3.75708181	0.05707302	0.00017191
s _a	0.108	Goodman test: 3.81897105	0.05614811	0.00013401
s _b	0.067	Reset all	Calculate	

Moderation Effect (H9& H10)

Testing the moderating effect of this study was done also based on the CR and P results of SEM as shown in Table 5 below.

**Table 5
Moderation Effect Test**

			Estimate	SE	CR	P
Loyalty	<---	Product Quality	0.235	0.096	2,225	0.026
Loyalty	<---	Price	0.358	0.092	2,439	0.000
Loyalty	<---	Interest	0.536	0.067	4,427	0.000
Loyalty	<---	Interaction1	0.011	0.000	3,904	0.000
Loyalty	<---	Interaction2	0.009	0.000	3.987	0.000

Source: Primary Data Processed, (2022)

Testing the first moderating effect on the moderating role of Interest on the Product Quality influence on Loyalty. The test provides the coefficient 3 = 0.536 with a significance of 0.000, where interest affected loyalty. While the coefficient 5 = 0.011 with a significance of 0.000, where the interaction between interest and product quality also affected loyalty. This shows that interest quasi-moderated (as a quasi-moderator) the Product Quality influence on Loyalty (H9 is accepted).

The second test of the moderating effect on the moderating role of Interest on the Price influence on Loyalty. The test provides the coefficient 3 = 0.536 with a significance of 0.000, where interest affected loyalty. While the coefficient 6 = 0.009 with a significance of 0.000, where the interaction between interest and price also affected loyalty. This shows that interest quasi-moderated (as a quasi moderator) the Price role in Loyalty (H10 is accepted).

V. Conclusion

The result shows Product quality affected satisfaction, Price affected satisfaction, Product Quality affected Loyalty, Price did not affect Loyalty, Interest affected loyalty, Satisfaction affected loyalty, Satisfaction partially mediated the product quality role in loyalty, Satisfaction fully mediated the price role in loyalty, Interest (quasi)

Moderated the Product Quality role in Loyalty, and Interest (quasi) Moderated the Price role in Loyalty. These findings prove that the loyalty-strengthening model for iPhone users in Banda Aceh city is a function of increasing product quality and price compatibility, which is strengthened by increased interest, and also with the contribution of increased satisfaction. This explains that the model in this research has been tested. The novelty is in the combination of previous models which are integrated to be proven on the current research subject, namely iPhone users in Banda Aceh city. This model can be used as a basis for further research, and strengthening of theory for academics. This model is also useful for practitioners, especially for iPhone distributors in Banda Aceh city so they can manage their sales. Some recommendations are generated from the research data. To increase consumer loyalty for iPhone customers, sellers in Banda Aceh must continue to present innovative products branded iPhone in their stores to reach the market. In increasing loyalty, sellers in Banda Aceh must also pay attention to the service factors they provide so that they are of good quality and smart in providing competitive prices.

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